

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ADOLESCENT PERIOD

Eyyubova R.

*Senior Lecturer, PhD in Psychology
Sumgayit State University, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

One of the serious changes that occur in adolescents is the changes in their emotional sphere. The volatility of emotions and feelings makes them difficult to control and leads to the weakening of the adolescent's self-reflection and self-control. The constant and intense manifestation of feelings is also characteristic of the adolescent age period. In general, the feelings of the adolescent are almost always contradictory. Any minor injustice upsets them, and the adolescent shows a behavior that does not take into account the final result. Therefore, when influencing the adolescent's personality, the strong influence of feelings and emotions on behavior should be taken into account. Because feelings help resolve psychological conflict by giving priority to one of the competing demands. Of course, only optimal emotional tension prevents a sober and correct analysis of the situation and results in mistakes. In addition, negative emotional states are also dangerous for mental health. Therefore, teachers and educators should refer to positive feelings and emotions when influencing the adolescent's personality. In this case, the teenager believes in the importance of "reconstruction", the necessity of "changing oneself" is perceived not as "renunciation of oneself", but as a move towards the desired goal. He tries to find his place in the collective, to establish a business and emotional connection with it. The teenager tries to be guided by his desires from the position of "necessity", which helps to resolve the psychological conflict, "reconstruct oneself", saves him from being influenced by his own demands, creates clarity of inner thought. There are also contradictions that are characteristic only of adolescence.

Keywords: physical changes, conflict, emotional connection, teenager.

During this transitional period, complex physical changes occur, which seriously affect the psychology of the teenager. Already more or less acquired life experience and existing knowledge allow him to move to a new level of behavior. The teenager, first of all, begins to perceive himself as a person. A sense of personal dignity manifests itself in a particularly pronounced form. He does not tolerate the approach to him with the dimensions of childhood, step-by-step guardianship. Excessive parental care, or unnecessary control and attempts to lead at every step, restrictions (if there are children aged 6-10 in the family) oppress the teenager even more.

Physical and mental development, new and higher requirements for the teenager at school and in the family create the basis for the development of an extremely important character trait in him - the teenager is already beginning to defend his right to independence, he tries to be like adults and wants others to feel that he has grown up, to reckon with him. At all ages, children want to seem grown-up, but if by adolescence this manifests itself in the form of a "big game", then the teenager often has the opportunity to behave like an adult and therefore seriously wants to be an adult.

The teenager is no longer an unspoken executor of the requirements of parents and teachers, like a younger schoolchild. He has his own opinion about life events, people, their behavior.

In general, the role of will in resolving both external and internal contradictions is great, and by regularly developing will, a teenager can regulate his behavior and relationships.

Contradictions are resolved in the process of activity, in communication with other people, especially with the collective. In the process of communication, a

teenager understands that social connections and the actions conditioned by them directly or indirectly affect his successes or failures. Only in communication with the collective does a teenager understand the meaning of his behavior for himself and for those around him. Therefore, it is extremely necessary to prepare a teenager to "study" his activities, to learn the attitude of others to him, to "see" his own advantages and disadvantages.

Taking into account the role of observation and self-observation in understanding the meaning and causes of mental conflict, it is necessary to direct the teenager to this, to form in him the ability to compare his observations with the observations of his peers, teachers and parents. This helps the teenager to understand the dependence of his "I" on social norms and rules and the importance of mastering them.

When studying the history of the study of Internet addiction in psychology, we determined that the mentioned problem was studied in different directions. In psychology, Internet use and extreme deviations during use, and ultimately the manifestation of Internet addiction, were evaluated as a current problem and were studied in different directions. The studies conducted in this area can be mainly grouped into the following directions:

1. Studies conducted in foreign psychology (America);
2. Studies of psychologists of a near foreign country, more precisely, Turkish;
3. Studies of Azerbaijani psychologists.

When studying the theoretical and historical issues of the study, we initially looked at the studies of American psychologists.

To this day, Internet addiction and its Many studies have been conducted on the effects of the Internet. In 1999, David Greenfield, director of the Center for Internet Behavior, conducted a study with ABC news.com and concluded that the services offered by the Internet increase the risk of users being exposed to disorders such as dissociation of identity, improper use of time, loss of reality, and instant gratification, and such situations are manifested in the daily lives of 6% of all Internet users. The Internet is an important tool that helps individuals to easily connect with each other, quickly establish relationships with other people without distance, and is a source of knowledge. Video conferences with people on the other side of the world via e-mail, obtaining knowledge from world libraries, instantly being informed about what is happening in the world, listening to music or watching movies, playing games, shopping without borders and without effort, and conducting financial transactions even from home - these are just a few of the countless things that the Internet has added to the lives of individuals[6;12].

However, when Internet use takes up most of an individual's time, the problem of Internet addiction has emerged. Internet addiction is manifested by symptoms such as not setting limits on Internet use, continuing to use it despite social or academic harms, and feeling deprived when the Internet is not available (N.A.Shapira, M.C.Lessig,T.D. Goldsmith, S.T.Szabo, M. Lazoritz, M.S.Gold, D.J.Stein, 2003)[6].

The vast majority of studies on Internet addiction in the psychological literature have been conducted with university students and adults. (I.J. Bakken, H.G.Wenzel, K.G.Götestam, A. Johansson, A.Oren, 2009; G. Ferraro, B. Caci, A.D'Amico, M. Blasi, 2007; L. Leung, 2004)[2].

However, due to the gradual increase in the number of adolescents as Internet users (K. Subrahmanyam, G. Lin, 2007)[7], various studies have been conducted in the last decade to investigate the facts about Internet addiction in adolescents (DiNicola, 2004; K.S. Jang, S.Y. Hwang, J.Y. Choi, 2008; K. Kim, E. Ryu, M-Y. Chon, E-J. Yeun, S-Y. Choi, J-S. Seo, B-W. Nam, 2006)[8].

While the Internet is emerging as a resource that facilitates adolescents' access to knowledge, research, and investigation, and at the same time develops skills such as problem-solving and critical thinking (I.Berson, M.Berson M, 2003)[5], on the other hand, it is also thought that it negatively affects personal skills due to excessive, aimless, and uncontrolled use. (J.Colwell, M.Kato, 2003; C.J.Kerber, 2005)[4].

Internet addiction is an addiction that can manifest at any age. However, adolescents are one of the most important risk groups here (Ö.Öztürk, G. Odabaşoğlu, D. Eraslan, Y. Genç, Ö.A.Kalyoncu, 2007)[8]. The intense interest of adolescents in technology leads them to use the Internet more than other age groups (T.Treuer, Z. Fabian, J. Füredi, 2001; L.Widyanto, M.McMurrin, 2004) [1].

Adolescence is a period when adolescents are at the center of cognitive, emotional and social development, which makes individuals a potential risk group

for Internet addiction (A.A.Ceyhan, 2008; C.Tsai, S.J.Lin, 2001; S.C Yang, C.J. Tung, 2007) [4].

C.Chou and M.C. In a study conducted by Hsiao in 2000 [6], it is noted that the increase in Internet use among adolescents reduces the time allocated for real social relationships and face-to-face meetings, causes social isolation, and it is observed that the loneliness of adolescents who use the Internet excessively increases.

American psychologists Y.A. Hamburger and E. Ben-Artzi revealed an interesting fact as a result of the studies conducted in 2003: it was proven that Internet addiction does not cause loneliness, but Internet addiction occurs as a result of loneliness.

X. Chen, F. Li, L.L.Long proved in their studies conducted in 2007 [5] that the observation of Internet addiction is high in schoolchildren with a low level of social support and that low social support is a risk factor for Internet addiction. When examining the theoretical and historical issues of the study, we initially looked at the studies of American psychologists, but at the same time, extensive research by Turkish psychologists in this field is also known to science. When we review the studies conducted by Turkish psychologists, we observed that studies on internet addiction started in the 2000s. Among these researchers, clinical psychologist Feyza Bayraktar (2001) investigated the impact of internet use in adolescence on the mental and social development of adolescents[8]. N.S.Ayaroğlu (2002) studied the relationship between internet use and loneliness among university students[2].

While investigating the study of internet addiction, it was found that adolescents (G.T.Kurtaran, 2003; A.Y.Tahiroğlu, G.G.Çelik, M.Uzel, N.Özcan, A.Avcı, 2008)[4] and university Studies that have studied the purposes of Internet use of university students (A.A. Ceyhan, 2008)[6], and in some cases, primary school students (A. Ersoy, Sh. Yaşar, 2003; F. Orhan, B. Akkoyunlu, 2004 attract attention.

While examining the studies that have studied Internet addiction in Azerbaijani psychology, we identified a dissertation by Gudsı Faranak Bahaddin entitled "Comparative social-psychological analysis of the behavior of schoolchildren using the Internet". The dissertation covered schoolchildren from Tehran and Baku (Gudsı Faranak Bahaddin, 2016). In the dissertation work, the socio-psychological issues of Internet addiction in schoolchildren in the modern era were investigated, the factors affecting the development of Internet addiction were systematized, and the psychological problems caused by Internet addiction on different ethnic grounds were analyzed based on a comparative social-psychological analysis. At the same time, the dissertation put forward theoretical and practical considerations for the effective use of technologies by schoolchildren and the preservation of their socio-psychological health, clarified the problems caused by Internet addiction in schoolchildren's behavior, determined the levels of the relationship between Internet addiction and social activity, and found a significant relationship between Internet addiction and suffering, depression, and physical health of school Internet users. It was determined that when Internet addiction is high,

depression increases, suffering increases, and health status weakens[2].

In general, when examining studies that have studied Internet addiction in Azerbaijani psychology, we determined that there are some articles, theses, and conference reports in this field. However, we did not come across a broad, fully and in detail experimental study that would explain the problem.

While working on the history of the study, one fact also attracted our attention: it is observed that there is a limited number of studies aimed at studying the symptoms that increase or cause Internet addiction, and these studies have come to the fore in the last 2-3 years. In this regard, there is a great need for studies that will study the factors that create Internet addiction. That is why we chose the problem of Internet addiction as the subject of research. In the research conducted by us, the age-sex determinants of Internet addiction in adolescents are determined, and the lifestyle indicators of adolescents with Internet addiction are reviewed. At the same time, the relationship between Internet addiction and depression and causeless anxiety is considered, and the level of depression and anxiety of adolescents with Internet addiction is determined. In this section, we reviewed the theoretical and historical issues of Internet addiction, or rather, the history of research on the problem by foreign psychologists, as well as psychologists

from a near foreign country, namely Turkish psychologists, and finally, the history of research on the subject in Azerbaijan.

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